

TREAT-AD

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PTPN6/SHP1 screening

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Structure-Based Virtual Screening of SHP1 Allosteric Inhibitors

Due to the ability to screen large and diverse compound databases at faster speed and lower costs compared to high-throughput screening, we decided to perform a structure-based virtual screen on the SHP-1 allosteric pocket using a previously reported full-length (FL) crystal structure (Yang et al., 2003]. We virtually screened the ChemBridge CORE library against the SHP-1 allosteric pocket (PDB 2B3O) using the Glide virtual screening workflow, followed by removing ligands with high strain (≥ 4 kcal/mol), clustering, and visual selection based on docking score, quality of putative interactions within the pocket, and synthetic accessibility. 78 compounds were purchased and subjected to the allosteric assay, yielding one hit, **75**, with 34% and 0% inhibition of FL SHP-1 and catalytic domain, respectively at 200 μ M (**Table 1**).

Table 2. Structures, ID number, and % inhibition of FL and catalytic (PTP) domain for virtual hit **75**.

Structure/#	% Inhibition FL @200 μ M	%inhibition PTP domain @500 μ M
 75	34%	0%

Assay development for biochemical HTS screening of SHP1 allosteric inhibitors

Assay development for HTS. The allosteric assay was optimized based on reported SHP2 allosteric assay (Chen et al. 2016). A 10-residue peptide from CD33 receptor (CD33_pY340), one of the SHP1 upstream, was utilized as the activating peptide to shift SHP1 from closed autoinhibited conformation to open active conformation. This allowed maximized signal-to-noise ratio and identification of small molecules that stabilize the autoinhibited conformation. The EC₅₀ and maximal fold activation of CD33_pY340 was determined to be 1.6 μM and 16-fold, respectively. The assay was optimized in both 96-well and 384-well plates for HTS and further *in vitro* characterization. An “excellent-range” Z score of 0.75 was determined for the optimized assay, was tested to confirm the assay’s utility for screening and IC₅₀ determination.

High-Throughput Screening. The allosteric assay was utilized to screen ~100,000 compounds from both CNS libraries (29,260 compounds) and structure diversity libraries (72,000 compounds) from chemical genomic facility. All compounds were screened at 20 μM against full-length SHP1. A counter screening against PTP domain was performed on compounds showing >30% inhibition (1,365 compounds) to rule out aggregators and active site directed inhibitors. Among the hit molecules, hits with >50% inhibition (454 hits) were identified as Tier 1 hits and prioritized and the activity against both PTP domain and full-length constructs were further validated. Compounds with reproduced activity (49 compounds) were repurchased to characterize their dose-dependence, mode of action, and binding properties etc.

Figure 1. Scheme of current HTS progress.

Among the hit compounds, a pyridone scaffold emerged as a moiety that allosterically inhibit SHP1. Several negative pyridone compounds were also purchased to generate a preliminary SAR for the scaffold once validated. The cherry picking of Tier 2 hits (925 compounds) with >30% inhibition but <50% inhibition is in progress.

Figure 2. Potency of representative pyridone compounds from the primary and counter screening.